

Original Article

HARNESSING TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF UNIVERSITY BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN SOUTH-EAST

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Abstract

The study determined Business Educator's opinion on the strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of university Business Education programme in South-East. The study adopted a survey research design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire entitled; Harnessing technological Innovations for effective Implementation of University Business Education programme Questionnaire (HTIFEIOUBEPQ). The instrument was validated by three experts. The reliability was done using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.68; indicating that the instrument is reliable. The population for the study consisted of 80 Business Educators from both federal and state universities in South East offering Business Education programme. There was no sampling since the population is manageable. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. Results of the data analysis relating to the study have shown that instructional and digital related strategies respectively will harness technological innovation for effective implementation of university Business Education programme in South East. Business Educators in federal and their counterparts in the state did not differ significantly on instructional and digital tools related strategies respectively. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Business Educators should be exposed to technological innovations. Again, the use of digital tools should be made compulsory to Business Educators

Keywords: *Technological Innovations, Business Education, Instructional Strategies, Digital Tools, South-East Universities*

Introduction

Technological innovations have transformed the business landscape and education. Effective integration of technology can enhance teaching,

learning and assessment particularly in Business Education programme.

Business Education programme has undergone significant transformations over the years driven by

advances in technology. Ugwunwoti, Eya and Aruah (2024), opined that, Business Education programme is a structured educational initiative that teaches students the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed to succeed in business, entrepreneurship and management; preparing them for careers in various business fields. Business Education programme equip students with competencies vital for success in the business world.

In the words of Nwosu (2020), Business Education programme is an educational process that prepare individuals for careers in Business, entrepreneurship and management. According to Okeke Ezeanyawu and Okpala (2021), Business Education programme is an educational programme that equips the recipients with the knowledge and skills for establishing and managing a business venture. The programme can be harnessed through technological innovations.

Harnessing technological innovations means using new and emerging technologies to improve and enhance teaching, learning and educational outcomes. Picciano (2020), stated that technological innovations popularly used in teaching are Learning Management Systems (LMS), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and Virtual and Augmented Reality (VA/RA). These will no doubt help in harnessing technological innovation for effective implementation of Business Education programme particularly with the needed strategies.

Strategies are long-term plans of actions designed to achieve specific goals or objectives. In Business Education, strategies refer to deliberate plans and approaches to achieve specific learning objectives; enhance students engagement and develop essential skills for future business professional (Ugwunwoti, et al, 2024). Moreover, Nwosu (2018), opined that strategies in Business Education involve the integration of teaching methods, learning techniques and assessments procedures to promote effective learning outcomes.

In this context, instructional related strategies and digital tools related strategies. With these strategies, technological innovations could be harnessed for the effective implementation of Business Education programme.

Instructional related-strategies no doubt, will harness technological innovations for effective implementation of Business Education programme. These are methods and techniques used to deliver ideas, model, design, specification, standard or policy. According to Olofuntoye (2023), implementation in educational setting is usually done by teachers who have to select the contents of the subject matter, methods of teaching, instructional resources and evaluate the possessed product of their functions in order to know whether or not the objectives have been met in the right direction. In Business Education, particularly in universities, implementation of Business Education Programme is done by the Business Educators.

A Business Educator is an expert in teaching and researching Business Education particularly in universities in Nigeria. Ekoh-Nweke and Ezeabii (2021) noted that, a Business Educator is an individual who has or obtained the professional qualification which enables him or her to be employed to lecture or teach in any recognized tertiary institution in Nigeria that offer Business Education programme and is physically fit of sound mind, and mentally alert.

Business Educator according to Ugwunwoti and Eya is the implementer of curriculum, and decides on what instructional materials to use, the methods to adopt, and the amount of time to spend on each aspect and the equipment as well as be more useful when technological innovations are harnessed for effective implementation of Business Education programme.

In South-East states of Nigeria, Business Educators are employed by both the states and Federal universities. State universities are owned, financed and controlled by state government. (Agbo and

Ugwunwoti, 2022). On the other hand, Federal universities are owned, financed and controlled by the Federal government. These Business Educators, irrespective of the ownership of the universities, are expected to pursue effective Business Education programme.

Regrettably, the Business Education programme in the South-East seem not to have attain the needed standard in term of implementation. A careful look at various offices where Business Education graduates work indicate that there are poor handling of digital tools. Again, some employers of labour have turned down applications from some of these graduates; as they may not function effectively in today's offices that are characterized by complex and even changing digital technologies.

Could it be that these graduates were taught without harnessing technological innovations? Is that Business Educators lack the needed strategies to harness the technological innovations, hence could not impart these skills on their students? It was in line with stated questions that the present study sought to determine the strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of Business Education programme in universities in South-East, Nigeria,

Statement of the problem

Effective implementation of Business Education programme, is the successful execution of a well-planned and well-designed programme that achieves its intended learning objectives and outcomes. Reports have it that, this programme is lacking in term of implementation.

Moreso, there are reports that traditional teaching methods and curricula are still in use. This may not adequately prepare students for the demand of the digital workforce, leaving them at a disadvantage in the job market.

Could it be that, many Business Education in universities may not be leveraging technological innovations effectively, resulting in inefficient use of resources and poor learning outcomes? Therefore,

there is need to reverse the trend by finding out the strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of Business Education programme. Hence, the following question, what then are these strategies? Finding answer to this question was the major concern of this study.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to determine strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of universities Business Education programme in south-east. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of university Business Education programme in South-East and;
2. Ascertain the digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of university Business Education programme in South-East.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East?
2. What are the digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East?

Hypotheses

The under listed hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Ho₂: There is significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively regarding digital tools strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. Descriptive survey design according to Nworgu (2015) is the one in which a group is studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The study was carried out in Federal and State Universities in South-East that are offering Business Education programme. The population for the study comprised of 80 Business Educators from six universities offering Business Educators. There was no sampling, because the population size was manageable.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled: Technological innovations for Effective Implementation of University Business Education Programme Questionnaire (TIFEIOUBEPQ). The instrument has three sections. Section A was on bio-data. Section B on the instructional related strategies and Section C contains items on digital tools related strategies. The rating responses were Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was evaluated by three experts; two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (measurement and evaluation), both from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu State. To test the reliability of

instrument, 20 Business Educators in government owned universities in South-South were used. Cronbach Alpha estimate was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument which yielded a coefficient index of 0.68; this index indicated the reliability of the instrument for the study.

The researchers with the help of six research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 80 copies were returned and used for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Mean with standard deviation were used in answering the research questions; while t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at the appropriate degree of freedom.

Decision rule for answering the research questions was based on the real limits of the mean thus:

Strongly Agree	-	3.50 – 4.00
Agree	-	2.50 – 3.49
Disagree	-	1.50 – 2.49
Strongly Disagree	-	1.00 – 1.49

For the hypotheses, when the calculated t-value was equal to or greater than the table value, the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise it was not rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1:

What are the instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators on the instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education.

S/N	Item Statement: Instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of university Business Education.	Federal n = 60		State n = 20		Overall n = 80		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}	SD	

1.	Deliver instructional context online (flipped classroom)	3.50	0.88	3.31	0.82	3.41	0.85	A
2.	Combine traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning (blended learning)	3.44	0.83	2.75	0.59	3.10	0.61	A
3.	Use game design elements, such as points, badges to engage students	3.23	0.61	3.21	0.68	3.22	0.65	A
4.	Organize virtual field trips to businesses using video conferencing	3.28	0.84	3.52	0.63	3.41	0.74	A
5.	Use interactive simulations to teach business concepts	3.15	0.80	3.49	0.61	3.32	0.71	A
6.	Ensure students have vital digital tools	2.86	0.87	2.92	0.96	2.89	0.77	A
7.	Utilize online platforms such as slack or Trello to facilitate group work and collaboration	3.20	0.96	3.12	0.98	3.16	0.97	A
8.	Use video lectures, tutorials, or case studies to deliver instructional content	3.20	0.99	3.19	0.92	3.11	0.96	A
9.	Leverage interactive whiteboards to create engaging, interactive lessons, promote student participation	3.30	0.94	3.12	0.97	3.21	0.96	A
10.	Develop mobile friendly instructional materials to support student learning on-the-go	3.20	0.75	2.92	0.88	3.06	0.81	A
	Clustered Mean/SD	3.24	0.88	3.16	0.82	3.19	0.85	A

Result data in Table 1 above, reveals that items 1 to 10 with series of 3.41, 3.10, 3.22, 3.41, 3.32, 2.89, 3.16, 3.11, 3.21 and 3.06 respectively are regarded as agreed by the respondents. This means that, instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implantation of Business Education programme. The grand mean value of 3.19 attested to that while cluster standard deviation of 0.82 shows homogeneity of opinion of the respondents.

Hypothesis 1

Status	No	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-table	t-cal	Decision
Federal	60	3.24	0.88	78	1.96	0.38	N.S
State	20	3.16	0.82				

There is no significant difference between the scores of Business Educators in Federal and state Universities respectively on instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Table 2: Summary table of t-test analysis of mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on instructional related strategies for effective implementation of Business Education programme in South-East.

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Table 2 shows that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom is 0.38; while the table value or critical value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This means that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Research Question 2

What are the digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education Programme in South-East?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviations of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effectively implementation of Business Education programme in South-East.

S/N	Item Statement	Federal n = 60		State n = 20		Overall n = 80		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X̄	SD	
11.	Utilize Learning Management System (LMS) to manage course content	3.13	1.03	3.04	1.02	3.09	0.50	A
12.	Leverage tools like Slack, Trello, or Asana to facilitate group work	3.23	0.82	3.24	0.84	3.34	0.83	A
13.	Use platforms like 200m, Google meet or Skype to deliver live lecturers	2.36	0.88	2.36	0.99	2.31	0.92	A
14.	Utilize tools like Bizsim, Capsim or Simulation Studio to create interactive sections	2.84	0.88	2.22	0.96	2.53	0.92	A
15.	Use tools like Tableau, Power BI, or Google data studio to teach data analysis	3.00	1.10	3.07	0.92	2.04	1.01	A
16.	Utilize platforms like Kahoot, Quiziet, or Exam soft to administer online quizzes, exams	2.96	0.99	2.94	1.04	2.95	1.02	A
17.	Use Digitation to help students showcase their works	2.81	0.89	2.86	1.03	2.84	0.96	A
18.	Leverage tools like Hootsuite, Sprout Social, or Buffer to teach social media matters	3.25	0.84	3.05	0.86	3.15	0.85	A
19.	Utilize tools like Classcraft, ClassDojo to create engaging interactive learning experiences	3.16	1.02	3.02	0.79	3.09	0.96	A
20.	Use platforms like Youtube, Vimeo to host tutorials'	3.12	0.86	2.92	0.82	3.02	0.84	A
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.99	0.93	2.86	0.95	2.93	0.88	A

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Table 3, shows that item 11 to 20 with mean scores of 3.09, 3.24, 2.31, 2.53, 3.04, 2.95, 2.84, 3.15, 3.09 and 3.02 respectively are regarded as agreed by the respondents. The grand mean value of 2.93, also attested to that; while cluster standard deviation of 0.93 shows homogeneity of opinions of the respondents.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively regarding digital tools

Status	No	X̄	SD	Df	t-table	t-cal	Decision
Federal	60	2.99	0.93	78	1.96	0.48	NS
State	20	2.86	0.95				

Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom is 0.48; while the table value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since, the calculated t-value is less than the critical or table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This invariably means that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal universities and their counterparts in the state on digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 1, showed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities in South-East were in agreement that instructional related strategies harness technological innovations for effective implementation of Business Education programme. These strategies are, organize virtual field trips to business using video conference, use interactive simulations to teach business concept, use of game design elements among others. The findings are in line with Okorie (2019) that instructional strategies enhance achievement of instructional objectives. The null hypothesis one tested on the

related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

Table 4: Summary table of t-test analysis of mean scores of Business Educators in Federal universities and their counterparts in state type on digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East.

instructional strategies showed that, there was no significant difference between the scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities on instructional related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of university had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research question two, revealed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities in South East were in agreement that, digital tools related strategies harnesses, technological innovations for effective implementation of University Business Education programme.

The null hypothesis two tested, showed that Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in state in South-East did not differ significantly in their mean scores on digital tools related strategies for harnessing technological innovations for effective implementation of Business Education programme. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that, the

status of universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that harnessing technological innovations will ensure effective implementation of University Business Education programme in South-East contrary to the reports trending that Business Education programme in universities can survive without the needed innovations.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that:

1. The use of digital tools should be made compulsory to the University Business Education.
2. Instructional based teaching by Business Educators should be encouraged.
3. Authorities concern should organize regular seminars on technological innovations for practicing Business Educators.

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